

Note on the Anomalous Redox Potentials of Sulphydryl-Disulphide Systems.

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The history of this subject commences with the work of Dixon and Quastel (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 2943) who found that the following equation described the potential set up at an 'inert' electrode immersed in a solution containing RSH and RSSR,

$$E = E_0 - \frac{RT}{F} \ln [\text{RSH}] + \frac{RT}{F} \ln [\text{H}^+] \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (i)$$

Attempts to explain the anomalous redox potential have been made by these authors who suggested that the true oxidant might be something different from RSSR and that its concentration would have to be fixed by Dixon (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1927, **B**, 101, 57) who found E_0 to vary with the electrode metal, and correlating E_0 with the hydrogen over-voltage, applied Wieland's theory of hydrogen acceptors with a supposed equilibrium diffusion of hydrogen from the electrode surface; by Barron, Flexner and Michaelis (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1929, 81, 743) who assumed that a small constant amount of oxygen present allowed a cysteine (RSH) solution to attack a mercury surface, thereby producing a small constant quantity of a weakly dissociating compound, the mercury electrode functioning as one of the second order for RS^- ions; and by Ghosh and Ganguli (*Biochem. J.*, 1934, 28, 381), who believed that a film of oxygen or of an oxide, present on a mercury surface, permits a reaction with RSH in solution with the formation of mercury compounds, the electrode functioning in the manner visualised by Barron, Flexner and Michaelis (*loc. cit.*).

Ghosh, Raychaudhuri and Ganguli (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 43), observed that if a cysteine (RSSR) solution were partially reduced electrolytically at a mercury surface, the resulting solution would set up a potential of the normal redox form at that surface. Green (*Biochem. J.*, 1933, 27, 678) confirmed this, but found that if a new mercury electrode were introduced, the 'anomalous' potential was established, and, therefore, ascribed the 'normal'

potential to the presence of a compound at the mercury surface that was employed in the reduction. Ghosh and Ganguli (*loc. cit.*) found that the 'normal' potential was established at a mercury surface that had first been heavily polarised cathodically, and thus came to their above mentioned conclusions concerning the origin of the 'anomalous' potential, the establishment of the normal form being attributed to the use of a surface from which the oxygen or oxides had been removed.

In these attempts (except Dixon's, *loc. cit.*) to explain the 'anomalous' potential, there is required a constant concentration (or activity) in the solution, of an oxidant or of a heavy metal compound, according as to whether the electrode is visualised as functioning (a) as an inert electrode in a redox system, or (b) as a metal electrode of the second order for RS^- ions.

It may be pointed out that the required constancy in both these visualisations need apply only to the immediate neighbourhood of the electrode surface, but it is necessary to invest this region, regarded as a separate surface phase, with some peculiar properties. In case (a) it must be assumed that electrons only are engaged in the transfer of electricity between the metal and the surface phase, whilst ions only are so engaged between this phase and the bulk solution, and that the oxidant (possibly RS) is confined to the surface phase. In case (b) it must be assumed that ions of the metal are engaged in the transfer between the electrode and the surface phase but not between the surface phase and the bulk solution, and that the compound is confined to the surface phase.

The first case provides a ready explanation for the observations of Michaelis and Flexner (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1928, 79, 689) who, in a series of most carefully conducted experiments, found that the potential varied but little with the electrode metal (mercury, smooth platinum, and gold-platinum) and thereby dismissed Dixon's explanation (*loc. cit.*).

Actually, however, it seems that the simplest physical picture is obtained by merging the two visualisations and assuming that the RS radicles are combined with the surface metal atoms, forming a surface compound; the postulated constant activity of oxidant or compound being dispensed with altogether. It is supposed that the RS radicles are RS^- ions whose charges reside in the metal, and that in consequence of a vibrational motion, the bound ions can escape into the solution when their kinetic energy in an outward movement exceeds

a critical amount. They leave the metal with a deficiency of electrons, and equilibrium is established when the rate of loss of RS^- ions by the covered fraction of the surface equals the rate at which RS^- ions from the solution combine with the bare charged fraction. The electrode is regarded as a sort of first order 'RS electrode.'

For simplicity it is assumed that the R radicle itself has no dissociating groups, that there is no orientation of solvent molecules at the surface and the surface compound has negligible dipole moment, and that whilst all negative ions striking the bare charged surface may be held there the RS^- ions alone are bound to any appreciable extent. In order to allow for metal-metal junction potentials it is convenient to imagine the electrode metal (at electrical potential E_m) connected with some reference metal (at potential E_r). The potential difference $E_r - E_s$, where E_s is the potential of the bulk solution, is the one with which we are eventually concerned.

From Butler's (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1924, 19, 729), application of classical statistical mechanics to first order metal electrode systems the following approximate equations, (ii) and (iii), are readily developed, and Richardson's thermionic equation yields (iv),

$$N_1 = (n-x) \gamma \sqrt{RT/\pi W'_1} e^{-W'_1/RT - (E_m - E_s) F/RT} \quad \dots \quad (ii)$$

$$N_2 = \frac{x N_0 C}{n \cdot 1000} \sqrt{RT/2\pi M} e^{-W'_2/RT - (E_s - E_r) F/RT} \quad \dots \quad (iii)$$

$$E_r - E_m = \frac{W_m - W_r}{F} + \frac{RT}{F} \ln \frac{k_r}{k_m} \quad \dots \quad (iv)$$

where N_1 is the number of RS^- ions lost per second per cm.^2 of surface, and N_2 is the number gained from the solution; γ is a mean frequency of vibration of the bound RS^- ions; R , T and F have their usual significance; E_s is the potential at the 'balance point' at which an RS^- ion experiences equal attraction for the surface and for the solution; N_0 is Avogadro's number; M is the gram-ionic weight of the RS^- ions and C is their concentration in gram-ions per 1000 c.c.; W'_1 and W'_2 are the 'non-electrical' fractions of the work N_0 RS^- ions must do just to reach the balance point from the surface and from the interior of the solution respectively; n is the number of RS^- ions per cm.^2 of surface when the layer is complete, and x is the number that have left the surface; W_m and W_r are the energies absorbed in the separation of

N_0 electrons from the electrode and reference metals respectively, and k_m and k_r are constants characteristic of the metals.

At equilibrium $N_1 = N_2$, and hence from (ii) and (iii),

$$E_m - E_s =$$

$$\frac{W_2 - W_1}{F} + \frac{RT}{F} \ln \frac{1000 n \gamma}{N_0} \sqrt{\frac{2M}{W_1}} + \frac{RT}{F} \ln \frac{n-x}{x} - \frac{RT}{F} \ln C \dots (v)$$

in which $W'_2 - W'_1$ in the first term on the right has been replaced by its equivalent, $W_2 - W_1$, W_1 being the energy absorbed in the separation of N_0 RS^- ions from the surface, and W_2 , the energy evolved in their hydration; and W'_1 under the root sign in the second term has been replaced by W_1 as an approximation.

One consequence of the assumptions that have been made is that the p. d. $E_m - E_s$ must result from the separation of the RS^- ions from the surface and hence that it could not be negative, and the Helmholtz equation gives,

$$E_m - E_s = Hdx \dots (vi)$$

where H is a constant (1.8×10^{-6} volt/cm.) and d is a mean equivalent *vacuo* separation of the positive charges from the separated RS^- ions or their equivalents in the solution. Although d may vary somewhat, it will be assumed constant for the present purposes and given the value 10^{-8} cm. as representing its order of magnitude. Substituting (vi) in (v) it is seen that x increases continuously as C decreases, but it is not possible to express x or $E_m - E_s$ as an explicit function of C . From (vi) it is seen that an increase of 0.5 volt in $E_m - E_s$ requires an increase of about $3 \cdot 10^{13}$ in x . On the other hand, n , identified with the surface concentration of metal atoms, is of the order 10^{15} , and hence, unless x or $n - x$ were initially very small, the first three terms on the right in (v) could be replaced by a constant, E'_0 , for any one metal over a very wide range in C .

The magnitudes of most of the quantities appearing in (iv) and (v) are either unknown or are known only approximately. The second term on the right in (iv) is usually considered insignificant in comparison with the first. Setting $T = 300$; $M = 100$; and (from consideration of the 'residual ray' frequencies of elements and compounds, heats of ionisation of various compounds, heats of hydration of ions,

the photo-electric effect and thermionic emission) $\gamma = 10^{13}$ sec.⁻¹; W_1 , W_2 , W_m , $W_r = 10^6$ joules. as possibly representing their orders of magnitude, it is found that the second term on the right in (v) is of the order +0.3 volt and that its variation with the electrode metal will perhaps be slight. In as much as a large change in $E_m - E_s$ requires only a small proportional change in x or in $n - x$ when neither of these quantities is very small, the third term on the right in (v) can perhaps likewise be expected to vary but little, and under these circumstances $E_r - E_s$ would be substantially independent of the electrode metal if $W_m - W_1$ were constant. This, possibly, is not an unreasonable condition; a considerable part of W_1 must be represented by W_m , and the remainder may not vary much with similar metals.

In the simple instance dealt with in this outline of a possible mechanism for the 'anomalous' potential, the quantity C , or (without sensible error) $[RS^-]$, is related to the total RSH concentration, through the stoichiometric dissociation constant of the sulphhydryl group (k), and in place of the last two terms on the right in equation (i) there is obtained,

$$-\frac{RT}{F} \ln [RSH] + \frac{RT}{F} \ln [H^+] + \frac{RT}{F} \ln (1 + k/[H^+]).$$

If k is given the value $10^{-10.28}$, corresponding with one of the constants obtained by Cannan and Knight (*Biochem. J.*, 1927, 21, 1387), from electrometric titration of cysteine, the new equation fits the data of Michaelis and Flexner (*loc. cit.*) rather well. The precise significance of this agreement into a region where equation (i) fails with cysteine ($p_H > 9$), is obscure because of the presence of an amino and a carboxyl group in this compound. Barron, Flexner and Michaelis (*loc. cit.*) ascribed the departure above p_H 9 to an alteration in the composition of their postulated weakly-dissociating metal compound, whilst Michaelis and Flexner (*loc. cit.*) believed it to be associated in some way with dissociation at the sulphhydryl group.

Systems that could furnish 'anomalous' potentials in the manner outlined above are not excluded from the 'normal' redox category if electron change between their species and the electrode is precluded by formation of the surface compound. The 'normal' potential would then be established if formation of the compound were prevented and electron exchange were, at the same time, possible.

The surface compound could have its origin in a reaction of RSH with the surface metal atoms, or in dissociation of RSSR on the

surface, or in a reaction of RSH with oxygen attached to the surface. Unlike the first two, the last mentioned possibility does not accord with the work of Michaelis and Flexner (*loc. cit.*) who found excellent recovery of the 'anomalous' potential from pronounced cathodic polarisation of the electrode, nor can it be reconciled with their observation that the potential is fairly well established with a black platinum electrode that has first been saturated with hydrogen and then washed with nitrogen while immersed in the cysteine solution. In reference to the first two possibilities on the other hand, although the heavy cathodic polarisation at a mercury surface, employed in the electrolytic reduction of cystine, would presumably replace the RS radicles with a layer of hydrogen atoms, it seems rather unlikely that the layer would be sufficiently stable to permit the establishment of even a drifting potential of the normal type.

SUMMARY.

The establishment of the anomalous redox potentials of sulphhydryl-disulphide systems, is attributed to the ionisation of a surface compound, formed by the combination of RS radicles with the surface atoms of the electrode metal.

A simple theory of the 'surface compound' electrode is given.

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Parachors and Chemical Constitution. Part VI. Quadrivalent Tellurium Compounds.

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Lowry and Gilbert (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 2867.; Sidgwick, "The Covalent Link in Chemistry," 1933, p. 206; Lowry, "Optical Rotatory Power," 1935, pp. 58-59) prepared optically active forms of phenyl-*p*-tolylmethyltelluronium iodide. This led them to conclude that quadrivalent tellurium, like quadrivalent sulphur and selenium, possesses a tetrahedral configuration.